

MODERN INNOVATION CAPABILITIES TEACHING FUNDAMENTAL DISCIPLINES

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Annotation.

The authors provide data on modern innovative opportunities that can be used to teach fundamental disciplines. Modern innovative educational opportunities used in the pedagogical process, as a result, not only bring the educational process to a new qualitative level, but also increase the level of students' knowledge. Combination with extracurricular independent work of students with educational material and writing notes on important sections of the topic of the practical lesson. The purpose of the training is realized, and students receive fundamental basic competencies that will be necessary for future work in their chosen medical specialty.

Key words

innovative, opportunities, fundamental, disciplines.

Fundamental sciences in the system of higher medical education rightfully occupy their significant place. At the same time, modern innovative opportunities provide undoubted advantages in the way of training highly qualified doctors, while the educational component of the educational process is also important. The latter includes a set of activities for students to master the skills of correct behavior from the point of view of deontology and ethics of a medical worker [1, 2, 3].

The study of fundamental subjects is important because they precede the direct entry of students into the clinical part of the training, for example, practical classes in pathological anatomy are held on the basis of the existing pathoanatomical department, in other words, in the morgue [4], classes in biochemistry and physiology can be held in existing hospital clinic laboratories.

A huge array of educational and scientific information that needs to be learned for each weekly lesson is a common problem area. Difficulties also relate to a large number of special words - terms that are often unknown to students before the start

of classes. An integrated methodological approach based on individual pedagogical skills, patience and high professionalism in a fundamental specialty allows us to overcome this problem [5, 6].

Other methods are also used. So, already at the first lesson, students are invited to independently work with educational material and keep notebooks with short notes - notes, which reflect the main sections of the topic of the upcoming practical lesson. For this type of extracurricular work, a set of textbooks and manuals is offered [7].

Innovative possibilities of the pedagogical process include extracurricular preparation of presentations on selected issues of the topic of the lesson being studied. During the classroom, students are given time for a report, this approach solves many issues in achieving a good level in the ability to show their work [7, 8].

The positive effect can be described as follows.

1. Preparation of a speech in the form of a report - presentation contributes to sustainable abilities in the analytical processing of literature. Particular attention should be paid to the fact that the search for the necessary information is not limited to educational literature, but the search for additional data, both textual and demonstrational, is stimulated. It is necessary to support the text part of the presentation with visual material.

2. A very useful experience of public speaking is acquired. It is a well-known fact that the fear of public speaking ranks first after the fear of death. Constant performances with presentations help to overcome this moment.

3. Gaining the skill to speak correctly and beautifully, to answer questions from the audience, will be necessary for the future doctor throughout his life in the profession and beyond. The ability to give a confident reasoned answer, to be able to correctly defend one's point of view - this is the valuable experience that is gained during educational presentations.

4. Demonstration of the key points of the processes under consideration in the form of brief and meaningful presentations, makes it possible for other students to better understand and master the issues under study.

The need to take notes during lectures is also instilled, while the lecture notes contain the necessary and fairly brief information on the topics of the subject. Lectures are conducted using modern media tools, which, in turn, contributes to the assimilation of educational material.

When studying a number of fundamental disciplines, an important part of the practical training is the demonstration of certain processes of the human body. So, today, innovative capabilities make it possible to replace the demonstration of

pathological changes in diseases on macropreparations and micropreparations under a microscope with digital analogues, which are more convenient and modern. The study and presentation of materials on the electronic board adequately replaces this part of the educational process [4].

Such a learning process develops the ability of students to analyze, synthesize conclusions and conclusions and, very importantly, makes it possible to train the ability to correctly present information in an academic style during presentations in practical classes.

The close interaction between the teacher and the student fits into the modern paradigm, when the student himself actively forms his knowledge. The function of the teacher in this case is to provide advisory pedagogical and methodological assistance. In general, this form also pursues another goal - the integration of the acquired fundamental knowledge into the practice of the clinical activity of the future doctor, the acquisition of the necessary clinical and anatomical thinking [7].

The huge variety and complexity of pathological processes and diseases, as an example, is demonstrated in such a common disease as atherosclerosis [9, 10, 11]. The need to study and the importance of this pathology is explained to students from the point of view of the socio-economic damage to society, tk. cardiovascular diseases associated with atherosclerosis are in the first place among the causes of mortality in the world population [12, 13].

On the other hand, one can really state that a solid base has been formed for the growth of students' professional competencies, in particular, in the difficult reality of establishing a diagnosis for patients for further strategies and tactics for the treatment and prevention of diseases.

The use of modern innovative capabilities of the pedagogical process results not only in an increase in the amount of knowledge, practice shows that they quickly become obsolete, but, importantly, the quality of the educational process improves. At the same time, students receive fundamental basic competencies, which make it possible to both obtain high-quality knowledge and successfully apply them in the chosen specialty of a doctor.

We consider it very important that the availability of searching for the necessary information on the Internet makes it possible to simplify the search for the necessary material for independent extracurricular training. We draw your attention to the fact that we consider the participation of the teacher in this process necessary to help in the correct search for information.

As a conclusion, it must be said that the training of a future doctor should not be limited only to gaining knowledge. We also consider it obligatory to form

universal ethical, cultural skills, psychological abilities to communicate with patients and their relatives and friends. These competencies will allow doctors to independently assess situations and find the right solutions in their future professional activities.

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